

FROM THE HISTORY OF ANIMAL HUSBANDRY AND NATIONAL VETERINARY SERVICE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The independence of our country created an opportunity to objectively illuminate the past of our nation based on historical sources. Special attention was paid to the study of the veterinary service of our nation, which has been a herdsman since time immemorial, among the oldest stone inscriptions, inscriptions and more than 20,000 manuscripts. The scientific study of these sources, their research, and the educational value of presenting them to the personnel of the veterinary field are important. After all, having knowledge of the history of the veterinary service of the people of Uzbekistan has a great impact on the further development of the field, and serves as a powerful tool in the formation of a modern veterinarian as a highly moral, loyal, responsible and patriotic staff.*

Keywords: *people's veterinary service, paintings on rocks, animal husbandry, archeological findings, inscriptions, manuscripts, domestication of animals, livestock, Sarmishsay, paintings on rocks, "Avesta", Amir Temur and the Timurid period.*

INTRODUCTION

Archeological material culture findings from the period of the ancient primitive community system of our country's history, as well as paintings on rocks and early historical sources in inscriptions, testify that our ancient ancestors protected livestock from various diseases based on the domestication of a number of hunting and animals. The use of treatment methods, the identification of medicinal plants (animals used these plants or various bodies under the influence of natural instinct, which people learned by observing them), and the use of folk medicine methods have become more and more widespread. Over the years, centuries, periods, such actions have been improved, and as a result, the service of veterinary medicine in animal husbandry has appeared and formed.

Photos and pictures of animal husbandry and veterinary medicine service engraved on ancient rock stones Sarmishsay, Karajontog, Ugom, Koksuv, Chotkal, Kurama, Morguzor, Nurota, Oktog, Koratog, Ohalik, Zirabulok, Bobotog and dozens of rocks, gorges, streams, caves in our country. and monuments such as Ungurs are among them. The pictures, paces, content - essence, characteristics, stylistic directions, period structure in them are colorful and directly refer to the famous Ingara, Lena, Enisei, Baikal, Orti, Amur, Ural, Karelia, Kabistan, Africa's Sahra-Kabiri, Spain and France rocks. It is characterized by dependence on the worked pictures, similar sides, and proportionality.

Animal husbandry played an important role in the life of the ancient herding tribes of Central Asia, and horses were used for various purposes. They were used to protect them from all kinds of diseases, breed healthy and strong horses, and even to attract someone with good intentions and goals. For example, in the decorations in the palace of the Achaemenid king Cyrus, pictures of Central Asian horses being drawn by the Sakas as a gift to the Achaemenids are shown. This shows that yearling is important in animal husbandry.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Horse-riding continued throughout the second millennium BC and at the beginning of the 1st millennium throughout Central Asia - the states of ancient antiquity - Dovan (Fergana), Shosh (Tashkent), Sugdiyona (Samarkand, Bukhara and a number of other regions, in general Zarafshan oasis), Bactria, Khorezm, Parthia, Margiyona and the adjacent places, according to historical data, yearling was widely developed, and various breeds of argumos were grown. Horses were cared for in separate pastures and various diseases were prevented and treated. In the 8th-9th centuries BC, the Assyrians took the thoroughbred horses of Central Asia and a large number of herds of yearlings, even during the reign of the Iranian Achaemenids, Bactria alone collected 30,000 head of yearling as a tax. Historical sources also testify that he led a thousand-strong cavalry and defeated Cyrus. The area between the two rivers of Central Asia and the areas adjacent to it were considered to be the center of domestication of horses and the developed center of thoroughbred horse treatment. In the care of horse breeding, it was considered the abode of folk healers who knew the secrets of keeping Ahal-taka, Yamud, Karabayir horses from various diseases.

The "Avesta", which is considered to be the golden book of our spiritual heritage, contains a lot of information about the history of the yearling. For example, "One wants a horse." Grandfathers soon became rich, strong, wealthy. Whishtaspchi? According to "Avesta" testified by the "Avesta", people in ancient times called "Yortiq ot tilar" healthy and strong horses, breeding and breeding of thoroughbred horses is a source of wealth and fame and a means of establishing a strong state. describes with That is, in one place in the "Avesta", if a character gallops on a three-horse horse, there are plenty of horsemen, and there are stately houses on the banks of every river, "the legendary flying horses" are called duldul (legendary flying horses). draws his attention to "a hundred cows, a thousand oxen, and innumerable cows".

RESEARCH RESULTS

Among the manuscript sources preserved in the funds of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Raikhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are dozens of sources in the field of veterinary science, but they were hardly studied during the time of the former Soviets. Among these manuscript sources, Aristotle's Treatise on the Selection of Horses, numbered 6558, 9799/11 and numbered 5694, 5203/11, contain the following valuable comments on folk veterinary medicine. In accordance with Aristotle's recommendation, Alexander of Macedon paid serious attention to the structure, habit, and behavior of a healthy horse when choosing horses, and prepared a manuscript on issues such as horse diseases, treatment methods, medicinal herbs, horse care, and how to do it in different seasons.

In accordance with this work of Aristotle, comparing his thoughts and opinions in the veterinary field with the life and experiences of the Middle East and Central Asia, the scientist Abu Bakr, Al-Manzir, who was known as "Veterinarian-Veterinarian", lived in the reign of Bahri Sultan an-Nasser Kalaun, the ruler of Egypt in the 14th century. al-Baytar (died 1248) in his "The Art of Identifying Diseases of the Horse" and "The Complete Book of the Art of Treatment in Veterinary Medicine and Animal Husbandry", the Egyptian (1344 - 1405 AD) Abu Baqa Muhammad ibn Isamuddin Ad-Damiri's "Life of Animals" in detail those who gave the analysis. The manuscript written by Abu Bako Muhammad ibn Isa ad-Damiri in 1371 is a scientific work rich in valuable information on zoology, which is based on the principles of the Arabic alphabet. The author of the work is used as a textbook of zoology in different schools in Egypt, criticizing the incorrect explanation of animal names to the students about the types, life, behavior, habits and

actions of animals. ends with At the same time, in this manuscript, biophysical characteristics of animals, characters, characteristics, dependence on humans, breed, type, types of diseases present in it, preparation of medicine, methods of treatment, legendary events of some animals, even the thoughts and attitudes of our Prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him, towards some animals. gives information about. In his work, the author also cites examples of folk veterinary medicine of ancient Greek and Byzantine scientists.

DISCUSSION

In the Middle Ages, excerpts from the book "Kitab al-khil al-baytari" (i.e. "About Horses and Veterinary Medicine") by Al-Jabali, a well-known scientist of his time, are used to comment on the unique and delicate aspects of veterinary and equine medicine, but the author It should also be noted that he did not set the goal of illuminating the history of veterinary medicine in his treatise. The Risola-yi asp ("Treatise on the Horse") belonging to Imam Muhammad ibn al-Hasani consists of 20 chapters, in which knowledge of a good horse, diligence of a horse, aging of a horse Valuable information is provided on knowing the best colors of a horse, knowing the sickness of a horse and what disease it has, treatment of a disease in a horse, treatment of a horse's cough, eye pain and its treatment, as well as the actions to be followed when riding a horse and knowing the badness of a horse. " ("The book about the horse") was written during the reign of Ubadullah Khan, one of the major representatives of the Shaibani dynasty, and was presented to him. It consisted of 15 chapters. They are devoted to knowing the sex, enthusiasm, enthusiasm and value of the horse, the parts and external signs of the horse, colors, behavior, how to treat the horse during the fight, and the diseases of the horse and their treatment. "Farasnama" ("Book about Horses"), copied in 1655 by an unknown author and composed of 70 chapters, decorated with gilded and colored lines and miniature paintings, written during the reign of the rulers of the Babur dynasty, is mainly a guide to the study of the causes of horse diseases and ailments. Translated from Sanskrit into Persian during the reign of Shahjahan, the rare manuscript consists of fifty chapters describing all aspects of the horse and is decorated with 29 miniature paintings.

CONCLUSION

It would not be wrong to say that until now, scientific researches and researches have not been carried out on the above-mentioned rare manuscript works and their authors, or on the texts translated from Greek, Sanskrit (ancient Indian language), Arabic, translated into Arabic-Persian languages. During the period of Amir Temur and the Timurids, important attention was paid to the field of animal husbandry and public veterinary service. From the "Tuzuklari Temur" and a number of other rare sources, unique and valuable historical information about cattle breeding can be obtained. In Amir Temur's work, which has a legal order, we pay special attention to livestock, especially horse breeding, and we can get information about horse breed, thoroughbred, that is, Arabian, Argumon types, as well as improving folk medicine and veterinary services in horse breeding. Amir Temur paid special attention to cattle breeding, camel breeding, donkey and mule breeding, and not only increased them and created special pastures, but also made extensive use of specialists with special knowledge and practical experience in the field of veterinary science of cattle, camels and sais. Those who raised them and paid serious attention to their education, established pastures for raising special breeds of horses for horse breeding, prepared military horses, and on these strong and durable horses, up to 800 thousand military men were involved in military action from one country to another quickly and organized in accordance with military

requirements. those who managed to act in an invisible state and achieved victory after victory. If Amir

Temur wants to go on a military campaign to any country, he should treat not only his soldiers and officers, officials and servants, and all the people participating in the military campaign, but also the horses, herds, donkeys, mules, camels and other animals used as transport from the public veterinary medicine. spent Horses, which were almost 3 times more than military troops, were bred for food, and millions of sheep were raised. A drop in the ocean from historical sources, the information given above shows the deep historical and spiritual roots of veterinary science in our country, and its study and knowledge is a proof of the dedication of every patriotic veterinary worker to his profession.

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